

NOTES

Coumarin Constituents of *Selinum tenuifolium*-1

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The isolation and structure elucidation of some novel coumarins, viz, selindin¹, vaginidin² and vaginol³, along with a new flavanone-selinone⁴ and a sesquiterpene-vaginatin⁵, occurring in *Selinum vaginatum* (Fam. Umbelliferae) were earlier reported. As no other *Selinum* species has been subjected to chemical investigation as yet, we became interested to examine another *Selinum* species viz, *Selinum tenuifolium* from chemotaxonomic consideration.

The air-dried powdered roots of *S. tenuifolium*, collected from Darjeeling area, were extracted with petroleum-ether (b.p. 60–80°). The concentrated extract upon chromatography over silica gel afforded three crystalline compounds A, B and C. Two of these compounds B and C, have been identified as the known furanocoumarins, heraclenin (1b) and bergapten (1c) respectively. Imperatorin (1a) has been found to be the major constituent of compound-A. The isolation and characterization of these furano-coumarins occurring in *S. tenuifolium* are described in this communication.

The pet. ether—benzene (1 : 1) eluates furnished a crystalline compound-A, m.p. 85°–86°. The latter displayed a broad spot on TLC plates indicating that it might be a mixture of two compounds. But attempts to separate compound-A by repeated graded chromatography as well as by preparative TLC were not successful.

The furanocoumarin nature of compound-A was indicated from its I.R. and U.V. spectra : λ_{max}^{EtOH} m μ 249, 297; ν_{max}^{NaCl} 1730 cm⁻¹ (coumarin lactone ring), 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring) and 1099 cm⁻¹ (benzofuran). The N.M.R. spectrum signals for a pair of doublets at 6.38 (J = 10 c/s) and 7.8 δ (J = 10 c/s) corresponding to C₃ and C₁ protons of a coumarin ring and another pair of doublets at 6.82 (J = 2 c/s) and 7.7 δ (J = 2 c/s) corresponding to β and α protons of a furan ring respectively suggesting the furanocoumarin nature of compound-A. An aromatic 1H-singlet at 7.38 δ was also discernible in the spectrum. A 2H-doublet at 5.0 δ (J = 8 c/s), a 1H-broad multiplet at 5.6 δ and a 6H-singlet at 1.7 δ

indicate the presence of an isopentenylloxy system ($-O-CH_2-CH = C \begin{matrix} \swarrow CH_3 \\ \searrow CH_3 \end{matrix}$). The above spectral data are in accord with a furanocoumarin skeleton having an isopentenylloxy side chain at either C₅ or C₃ position.

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The mass spectral fragmentation of compound-A was found to be similar to that reported for imperatorin⁶ (Ia). Compound-A suffers the same type of cleavage as that of imperatorin at the C₃-allylether bond giving rise to a base peak at m/e 202. Other prominent peaks appear at m/e 174 (m/e 202-CO) and at m/e 69.

- 1a. R = -H
 R' = -O-CH₂.CH = C $\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{matrix}$
- 1b. R = -H
 R' = -O-CH₂.CH-C $\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{matrix}$
 O
- 1c. R = -OCH₃
 R' = -H

Elemental analyses of compound-A gave C, 71.68 and H, 5.68% which are too high for imperatorin (C, 66.68; H, 4.72%). Hence from C, H analysis and variation in melting point it is readily apparent that the compound-A is a mixture of imperatorin (m.p. 101-2°) and a minor component whose gross structure also resembles that of imperatorin.

That the main component in compound-A is imperatorin was further proved by some chemical reactions. Catalytic hydrogenation with 10% Pd/C in ethanol furnished a compound, m.p. 248°, in good yield. The latter was identified as xanthotoxol, by m.m.p., co-TLC, U.V. and I.R. spectra comparison with an authentic sample. Hydrolysis of compound-A with glacial acetic acid-conc. sulphuric acid gave xanthotoxol. Compound-A on oxidation with perbenzoic acid in chloroform yielded an epoxy compound, m.p. 112-114°. The latter was found to be identical with an authentic sample of oxyimperatorin (m.p., m.m.p. Co-TLC, U.V. and I.R.).

Compound-B, m.p. 109-110°, was isolated from the benzene eluates as needles (CHCl₃-pet.ether), [α]_D+23° (C, 0.62, pyridine). It analyses for C₁₆H₁₄O₅ (Found: C, 66.98; H, 5.11%, C₁₆H₁₄O₅ requires C, 67.12; H, 4.93%); M⁺ 286; U.V. λ_{max}^{EtOH} mμ 249, 300 (log ε, 4.28, 4.02); I.R. ν_{max}^{nujol} 1735 cm⁻¹ (coumarin lactone ring), 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring), and 1100 cm⁻¹ (benzofuran). The N.M.R. spectrum of compound-B, besides showing the expected peaks of a furanocoumarin moiety, signals for two deshielded methylene protons at 4.6 δ (doublet, J = 6 c/s), a methine proton at 3.25 δ (doublet, J = 6 c/s) and two sharp methyl singlets at 1.2 and 1.4 δ. The NMR data suggested the presence of a

-O-CH₂-CH-C $\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{matrix}$ side chain to be present in this compound.

6. H. Budzikiewicz, C. Djerassi and D. H. Williams, *Structure Elucidation of Natural products by Mass spectrometry*, Holden-Day, Inc. Vol. 2, p. 259, 1964.

The above spectral data coupled with the optical rotation value showed similarities with those reported for heraclenin⁷ which was finally confirmed by comparing its I.R. and U.V. spectra as well as Co-TLC behaviour with those of oxyimperatorin (1b).

Compound-C, obtained from the earlier pet.ether-benzene eluates, crystallised from acetone-pet. ether as needles, m.p. 185-87°; $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$; M^+ 216; U.V. $\lambda_{max}^{Ethanol} m\mu$ 249, 268, 305 (log ϵ 4.23, 4.24, 4.23); ν_{max}^{KBr} 1735 cm^{-1} (coumarin lactone), 1640 (aromatic) and 1080 cm^{-1} (benzofuran). The N.M.R. spectrum, besides exhibiting the expected signals for a furanocoumarin skeleton, shows the presence of a $-OCH_3$ group at 4.48 δ . These physical data suggested compound-C to be bergapten (1c), which was finally confirmed by m.m.p. and Co-TLC behaviour with an authentic sample.

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